

**RESEARCH ARTICLE ON AJMODA FROM THE VIEW OF
AYURVEDA CLASSICS: A LITERARY REVIEW****Ajaya D. Yerne^{1*}, Mrunal R. Akre²**

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Article Received on 23 Sept. 2025,
Article Revised on 13 October 2025,
Article Published on 16 October 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17365913>

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How to cite this Article: Ajaya D. Yerne^{1*},
Mrunal R. Akre² (2025). RESEARCH
ARTICLE ON AJMODA FROM THE VIEW
OF AYURVEDA CLASSICS: A LITERARY
REVIEW World Journal of Pharmaceutical
Research, 14(20), XXX-XXX.

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ABSTRACT

Ajmoda is one of the best Medicinal drug which helps to improve gut health in very easy way by oral intake in day to day lifestyle in Indian culture. It is a spice and medicinal herb, used in Ayurveda for SHOOLPRASHAMANA and DIPANIYA from centuries. It is very much in used for its rich aroma and potent health benefits. *Ajmoda* contains thymol, a strong antibacterial, antimicrobial, antiseptic, antifungal and antioxidant property making its effective against infection. It is known for its ability to relieve menstrual cramps, headache and abdominal colic. It aids in boosting metabolism which helps in managing over weight and many more uses for recovering diseases. That's why, this drug need to focus for students, scholars and researcher. Hence, this review *Ajmoda*, i.e. *Carum roxburghianum* through various indications are in use, controlled trials are needed to determine its real efficacy. The

Ajmoda plant, its properties, mechanism of action and clinical uses are briefly was reviewed in this article.

KEYWORDS: Ajmoda, *Apium gravelons*, Carum seeds, *Carum roxburghianum.*, Celery, Shool prashaman, Vanya ajjmod.

INTRODUCTION

Carum roxburghianum linn (DC) Craib. is looking like AJWAIN which is 1-3 feet in height. It is profusely found in the geographical climate of Maharashtra, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh.

From here, it is supplied all over the world. It is an erect annual herb which has pinnate to bipinnate like leaves. Its flowers are small, creamy white, very much used in treatment of flatulence, stimulating digestive enzymes, broad spectrum antibacterial, increases metabolism to reduce weight, in Worms infestation, cleanses Urinary bladder, improves Cardiac tone, natural Aphrodisiac, etc. It is clearly mentioned in Laghutrays and Bruhatrays for successful result in treating all disease for human well being. Only scattered information exploring the drug is available and there is need to assemble it. So to revalidate the therapeutic claims of Ajmoda in the light of contemporary experimental and clinical studies this review was carried out.

Literature: Samhitas, Nighantus, Contemporary text and online studies available on Ajmoda. The current work appears to be first kind and can be considered as a reference standard for future studies.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Search Criteria: Knowledge of Ajmoda is available in our Bruhatrya as well as in laghutrya. First reference is available in Charak Samhita as well as Shushrut Samhita. Remaining reference from laghutraya like Bhavprakash, Dhanvantari Nighantu, Madanpal Nighantu, Nighantu Adarsh, Kaydev Nighantu, Rajnighantu. Also few published authentic researches mentioned in their articles, journals references of these were collected.

METHODOLOGY

As the drug was available in India, exact origin of Ajmoda is debated, it is believed to have originated in the Mediterranean region which has been grown in various part of the world. It is commonly known as Celery. Various parts of Ajmoda are used for its unique properties. The leaves, stalk and seeds are most commonly utilized parts for their culinary and medicinal benefits.

All Brihatryai- Charak Samhita mentioned AJMODA as best Shool prashamanas and Deepaniyas, works as the drug on various abdominal disorders i.e; improves digestion, menstrual cramps, metabolism, urinary bladder pain and worms infestation.

In Sushrut Samhita mentioned it as Pippalyadigana works as the best deepan as well as vatanuloman drug.

All Nighantus; It is mentioned as Agnidipak as well as Shoolprashaman.

- Ajmoda increases appetite
- Ajmoda has got a very strong aroma.

REGIONAL NAMES OF AJMODA

Celery (English)

Ajmoda, Ajmada (Hindi)

Vomma (Kannada)

Aayamodakam (Malayalam)

Ajmaoda Vova (Marathi)

Ajmoda Vova (Gujarati)

Randhuni (Bengali)

Asmatavomam (Tamil)

Ajmodavamu, TellaVamu (Telugu)

Fakhazur, Banjuan (Kashmiri)

Bonjamani Yamani, Ajowan, Bonajain (Assamese)

Karafs-e-Hindi (Unani)

Valjawain, Ajmod (Punjabi)

SCIENTIFIC CLASSIFICATION OF AJMODA

KINGDOM–Plantae

CLASS -Dicotyledons

SUBCLASS-Polypetalae

SERIES-Caliciflorae

ORDER-Umbellales

FAMILY-Apiaceae

GENUS-Carum

SPECIES-Roxburghianum

IMPORTANT PHYTOCONSTITUENT OF AJMODA

Seed:- Anthoxanthins, graveobioside A and B, Luteolin, Apioseglycosider, myristicin acid, Aprumetinumbelliferone, chrysoeriol.

Essential oil:- d-limonene, d-selinene, sesquiterpenealcohols, apigravin, sedanolide and sedanomic acid anhydride.

Thymol is a major component of oil of thyme and it's found in it.

Leaves and Tubers:- Aniinluteolin.

RASA PANCHAKA OF AJMODA

Rasa (taste):- Katu (pungent), Tikata (bitter)

Guna (virtue):- Laghu (light), Ruksha (dry), Teekshna (sharp)

Virya (potency):- Ushna (hot potency)

Vipaka:-Katu (Pungent)

Therapeutic administration and doses (matra) of ajmoda

Doses:-1 to 5 gm in churna form and

Distillate form 0.25 to 0.5 ml to

MAIN YOG AND ITS USES

Some important Yog in which Ajmoda is used as one of the best contain for treatment in various diseases explained in **AYURVEDA CLASSICS**. They are as follows:-

IN CHARAK SAMHITA

- 1) In Shadvirechanshatashtriy Adhyay used as Deepaniya and Shoolprashaman Mahakashaya.
- 2) In Santarpaniya Adhyay used in Trayushnadiyog.
- 3) In Yajpurushiya Adhyay explained as one of the best drug in 84Asav.
- 4) It is noted as Shirovirechan dravya kalpa-sangrah and Katuuskandh in Rogbhishakjitiyaviman Adhyay.
- 5) In Jwar Chikitsa ,it contains in Agurvadi Oil.
- 6) In Gulmnashak Yog, used in Hingvadi Churna and Gutika, Shatyadi Churna, Hingulsauvarchladhya Ghrut.
- 7) In Prameh used in Kapha pramehnashak dash Yog and also as Trikanttadhya Snehpan in Kaphaj and Vataj Prameh.
- 8) In Unmaad disease, used in Dvitiya Lashunadhya Ghrut.
- 9) In Swthyathu Chikitsa used in Phaltrikadhyarishta and also in Shaargudika.
- 10) In Arsh Chikitsa, used in Takrarishta.
- 11) In Grahanidosh Chikitsa, used in Chitrakadi Gutika and Vati and named it as also Panchamkshar.

- 12) In Madatyay Chikitsa used in Mrudvika Raga as Agnidipak.
- 13) In Yonivyapad Chikitsa, used in Pipalyadi Yog.
- 14) In Shyamatrivrutkalpa adhyaya, used in 18 yog of Nishoth and also in Kalyanak Gudh, Trivrutadi Modak.
- 15) In Snehavypad Chikitsa, it is used in Saindhvadi Anuvasan Oil.

In SushrutSamhita

- 1) In Dravyasangrahnii adhyaya ,it is one of the drug of Pippalyadi Gana.
- 2) In Mahavatvyadhi Chikitsadhyaya, used in Hingvadi Gutika for Adhmaan Chikitsa.
- 3) In Ashmari Chikitsa, used in Sharkaharyog.
- 4) In Bhagandar Chikitsa, used in Paniyadravya and Vednahar Shunthyadi Churna.
- 5) In Udar Chikitsa, used in Udar Roghar Samanya Yog.
- 6) In Mudgaarbh Chikitsa, used in Doshnirharanavum Vednahar Yog.
- 7) In Anuvasanottarbasti Chikitsa, used in Chitrakadi oil, Pathadi oil and Vidangdi oil.
- 8) In Naigmeshpratished Chikitsa, used for Dhupan in neonatal care.
- 9) In Atisarapratishedadyay, used in Pachan Yog, Shoolhar Yog and also used in Dipaniyadravya for Pravahika disease.
- 10) In Shoshpratishedadhyaya, used in AladiRasayana.
- 11) In Gulmapratishedhadhyaya, used in Chitrakadi Ghрут, Hingvadhy Ghрут, Rasonadi Ghрут, Paniya Ksharavleha, Kukshishoolhar Kashay.
- 12) In Hridrogapratishedhyaya,, used in Vatajhridroг Chikitsa Yog.
- 13) In Pandurogpratishedhayay, used in Vidangmustadhya Avleh.
- 14) In Panatyaypratishedhadhyaya, used in Vatik Madatyay Chikitsa.
- 15) In Kaaspratishedhayay, used in Kalyanak Gudh.
- 16) In Swarbhedpratishedhyay, used in Vataj Swarbhed.
- 17) In Visuchikapratishedhadhyaya, used in anya Visuchikahar Yog.
- 18) In Kaphaj Arochak Chikitsa, used with Madhu and other drugs for Vaman.
- 19) In Unmaadapratishedhadhyay, used in PhalghrutYog.

IN ASHTANG HRUDAYA

THERAPEUTIC USES OF AJMODA

- 1) In Shodhanadigansangrah Adhyaya, it is used with other drugs in diseases like Vataj, Kaphaj, Med, Gulm, Jwar, Shool and Arsh.

- 2) In Rajyakshmedi Chikitsa Adhyaya, used in Rasayana Yog and Aladi Sarpigud for disease like Prameh, Gulm, Kshyoga, Pandurog and Bhagandar Rog.
- 3) In Arsh chikitsaadhyaya, used in siddha ghrutyog and changeri ghrut nirmanvidhi for disease like anaha, mutrakruch, pravahika, gudbhransh, gudshool, arsh, grahani and vatshamak.
- 4) In mutraghatchikitsa adhyaya, used in panak for sharkarabhed.
- 5) In Gulmchikitsa adhyaya, it mixed with ghrut with other contain and in hingvashtak churna for vatajgulgulm.
- 6) In Bastikalpadhyaya, used with castor or sesame oil, saindhvadi oil for basti in diseases like kaphajrog, hernia, udavart, gulm, arshpleha prameha, urustambh, anah and arshhari for anuvasanbasti oil.
- 7) In Balaamaypratishedaadhyaya, used in siddha ghrutavleh for children's with diseases arises from mothers milk like vataj dushtijanyastanyapaan.
- 8) In Gulmpratishedadhyaya, used as one of the contain for drink in diseases like yonishool, parshvshool, hridrog, gulm, arsh
- 9) In Garbhvyapadshariradhyaya, it is used in decoction with other drugs mentioned for pain and excretion of retained product in mudgarbhnirharan.
- 10) In Jwarchikitsaadhyaya used in paste, decoction, sura, kanji with oil for application all over body in sheetjwara.
- 11) In Kaaschikitsaadhyaya, used in dipyadiyog, shadhavchurna and decoction with other medicine for kaphaj kaasa.
- 12) In Rajyakshmadichikitsaadhyaya, used with honey and other drugs in diseases like kaas,aruchi.
- 13) In madatyayachikitsaadhyaya, used as spice with animal flesh, other drugs and satu powder for curing disease like vatadhikmadatyaya.
- 14) In Aatisarchikitsaadhyaya, used in churna or paste, in aprajitajal, yavnyadi churna to cure pravahika for dipanpachan, stambhan and ruchikar. also in grahani, kshayrog, udarrog, swash and kaasrog etc.
- 15) In Grahanichikitsaadhyaya, used in vati with other drugs and lavanpanchadigutika to cure loss of appetite as pachak and agnidipak.
- 16) In Pramehachikitsa, used in siddhasneha with other drugs for single or sannipataj type of prameha.

- 17) In Gulmchikitsaadhyaya, used with ghrut and other drugs, hingvadi ghrut, hapushadi ghrut, lasunadi churna, hingvadi churna, vaishvanar churna, saindhvadi churna to cure vataj gulm for relieve pain and anah.
- 18) In Vatvyadhichikitsaadhyaya, used with other drug as paste, also nimbadi ghrut to cure sandhigatvat, asthimajjagat vayu, kusth, nadivran, arbud etc.
- 19) In Virechankalpadhyaya, used in kalyanakgud/avleha for kushth, arsh, kamlagulm etc.
- 20) In Balopcharniyaadhyaya, used with other drug for chatan to clear speech problem in children as vakshudhikaryog.
- 21) In Balamaypratishehdadhyaya used in decoction to cure vatdrushtijanyastanyaj diseases.
- 22) In Balgrahpratishedadhyaya, used in putyadidhupanwith other drugs to avoid balgrahabadha.
- 23) In Guhyarogpratishedadhyaya, used in kalk with other drugs, also in phalghrut to cure disease like yonidosh, shukradosh, garbhadharn, ayushyawardhak, buddhiwardhak, dhanwardhak etc.

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Sutrashan:-4/6, 4/25, 23/18, 25/48

Vimansthan:-8/142, 8/152

Sharirsthan:-NO ANY REF

Chikitsasthan:-3/266, 5/69, 5/79, 5/86, 5/87, 6/27, 6/38, 9/54, 12/39, 12/39, 12/43, 14/74, 15/96, 15/190, 24/181, 30/55

Kalpasthan:-7/16, 7/41, 7/52

Siddhisthan:-4/15

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Sutrasthan:- 38/22

Chikitsasthan:5/27, 7/18, 8/17, 8/38, 14/10, 15/20, 37/16, 37/36, 37/41

Sharirsthan:-NO ANY REF

Kapasthan:-5/63

Uttasthan:-36/7, 40/42, 40/80, 40/153, 41/50 42/25, 42/27, 42/32, 42/42, 42/127, 43/12, 44/28, 47/24, 47/25, 52/38, 53/11, 56/17, 57/8, 62/29

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Sutrasthan:-15/33

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Kalpasthan:-2/18 , 4/64

Uttarsthan:-1/49, 2/10, 2/12, 3/47, 34/30, 34/64

DISCUSSION

While studying the literature of Ajmoda, it was found that ajmoda is used in many general health significances to recover different types of abdominal diseases, very useful in obesity, as it is bitter and pungent in taste. it is good natural tonic as well as best in worms infestation. it can be used in urine infections, antibacterial, appetite stimulant. It can be used as best drug in missed abortion case for retained product during evacuation also, in abdominal cramp during menstruation. ajmoda is one of the important drug explained by Acharyas. it is described in deepaniya, shoolhar, pippalyadigadravya with numerous synonyms and basonyms.

CONCLUSION

Ajmoda is a common drug used in much Ayurvedic preparation which needs to be focussed. So all the available literatures was studied and compiled in brief for scholars, students and researchers so as to save time and increased the value of work. it is used as appetizer, abdominal colic and many more products can be prepared by the *Carum roxbarghianum*.

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